

Triple Whammy for the Muslims: *Poverty, Politics and the Pandemic*

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Abstract

The effects of the pandemic are felt by people across the globe. However, for marginalized and excluded communities such as Indian Muslims the effect has been devastating on many fronts including personal, economic and political. The community has been poor and backward through the last few decades. Additionally, the community has been denied a fair share in the welfare schemes owing to politics where in the name of secularism not much is needed to be done by the government other than pander to a few conservative religious voices. The political rise of Hindutva has led to normalization of political onslaught and exclusion of Muslims. There have been consistent attempts to communalize the pandemic. While the community reels under lack of awareness and education about the change required to cope with the pandemic, it is imperative that special steps are taken by the state agencies to rope in Muslims in the fight against the pandemic.

Keywords: Indian Muslims, poverty, politics, secularism, pandemic/ COVID-19

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The impact of the pandemic has been felt by people across the world in both developed as well as developing countries. The poor and marginalized communities continue to suffer greater hardships and losses owing to the severe health crisis as well as the economic destitution brought about by governmental measures such as social distancing and lockdowns in different parts of the globe. The pandemic has caused tremendous suffering to the poor who live on daily wages without any kind of social securities.

South Asia is home to over one-third of the world's poor population. It is not surprising that the pandemic has brought about intense suffering and greater socio-economic marginalization of the poor in the region. Many reports including one by Oxfam (Oxfam, 2021) highlight how the inequalities between the rich and the poor have increased since the arrival of the pandemic in early 2020 with the poor getting deprived of their meagre means of survival. Additionally, in the Indian sub-continent, the pre-existing fault lines along caste, religion and gender have exacerbated the effects of the pandemic. It would be naïve to assume that everyone is equally impacted by the pandemic; some historically marginalized communities such as Dalits, adivasis and increasingly Muslims have clearly borne a greater brunt.

In my opinion, Indian Muslims have experienced a greater impact of the pandemic owing mainly to two factors which are inter-connected: poverty and politics. I will attempt to provide an overview of both these factors here. It is not surprising for social backwardness and conservatism to flourish unchecked in a poor community existing on the margins of society. Besides, for many decades now, Indian Muslims have been at the center of a cynical politics of the supposedly secular variety on the one hand and divisive Hindutva on the other. Before 2014, different governments pandered to the conservative and patriarchal religious elements in the Muslim community in the name of

upholding secularism. The Shah Bano episode of 1986 is a stark example. In this kind of polity, genuine concerns of citizens such as education, health, jobs, civic amenities, representation get relegated as regressive conservative elements keep making nonsensical demands from the government. Eventually, ordinary Muslims get disenfranchised despite Constitutional safeguards. As though the whole of India's Muslims do not need anything beyond protection of regressive misogynist practices! Such politics gave rise to the Hindutva bogey of "Muslim appeasement" whereas in reality, certain north Indian mullahs and religious men were the only ones appeased. Over the decades it gained sufficient momentum for the Bharatiya Janata Party to come to power at the Center. Meantime, the Muslim masses have continued to live in poverty and backwardness. The political onslaught has persisted even during COVID-19 times with allegations of "corona jihad" in March 2020 on the Tablighi Jamaat gathering in Delhi and through various attempts to communalize the pandemic (Soman, 2021).

A Glance at Poverty and Exclusion before 2014

Muslims are the largest minority in India. According to the All India Religion Census of 2011, 17.22 crore Muslims comprise 14.23% of Indian population. The community has by and large remained poor and educationally deprived since Independence, different governments and economic policies notwithstanding. In the 1980s and 1990s there have not been many civil society organizations that engaged in working closely with the community or collecting data empirically. Official figures of the Government of India and the Gopal Singh Committee report in 1982 have documented the condition of poverty and low education as well as weak economic attainments. A more systematic effort was made by the Sachar Committee (Prime Minister's High Level Committee, Cabinet Secretariat, Government of India) which

published a comprehensive report on how Muslims fare poorly on all human development indicators. It highlighted that they live in poverty, without much education, without formal jobs, without access to government facilities on credit and without healthcare provisions. The Sachar report showed how only four in a 100 Muslims are graduates. It also highlighted that Muslim participation in salaried jobs was merely 13%. The report captured how Muslims lived with a sense of alienation, fear and insecurity owing to communal riots and violence in different parts of the country.

A national study conducted by us in 42 districts of 15 states across India found hardly any improvement in the lives of Muslims despite elaborate recommendations of the Sachar Committee and the PM's New 15-Point Program as well as the special program in the 90 Minorities Concentration Districts.

It can be seen that Muslims continue to be left out from educational support schemes, anganwadis, primary health care centres, below poverty line benefits, credit facilities etc. What is more, several ordinary persons voiced that there was a lack of a political will to include Muslims in the entitlements meant for the poor. Their feeling seems to be not unfounded as participation and inclusion of Muslims in various entitlement schemes meant for poor remains low.

Reproduced below is a sample about health care services across states in Muslim neighbourhoods surveyed by (Centre for Peace Studies (CPS)):

Table 1: Status of Healthcare Services in Muslim Neighbourhoods, across eight Indian states

State	HCs* with doctors (%)	HCs with nursing staff (%)	HCs with medicines (%)	HCs with emergency services (%)
Kerala	91	91	87	30
Karnataka	88	91	74	66
Madhya Pradesh	71	72	71	57
Jharkhand	71	72	54	22
West Bengal	74	63	64	50
Gujarat	70	68	41	16
Bihar	2	3	4	0.2
Haryana	13	0.5	4	0.0

Source: Centre for Peace Studies, 2014

*Healthcare Centres

Clearly, such a grim state of affairs pertaining to healthcare during ordinary times and particularly in states such as Bihar and Haryana cannot be expected to live up to the challenge of the currently raging pandemic.

In the Broken Promises survey (CPS, 2014), primary healthcare centres (PHCs) [which are envisaged as the first health contact point between communities and a doctor/ or medical professional], were reported to be accessible within their localities by just 22% of the respondents. Another 20% reported having sub-centres in their locality, 10% reported having cluster healthcare centres (CHCs) and 20% said they had other types of healthcare centres or facilities in their localities. Of this, 15% respondents further reported that the healthcare centres present were inactive in their village or locality. About 28% reported they had access to no public health infrastructure at all.

For a sizeable number of respondents, it was still acceptable to consider a health centre/facility active or functional even without a doctor or a nurse. It must be mentioned here that

in our interactions with the community a lot of women and girls said that they were treated very badly at many of these centres.

Only about 5% of the respondents reported that the Auxiliary Nursing Midwifery (ANM) worker in their locality was a Muslim. Even in a job like that of the ANM, where cultural factors are very pertinent, the low presence of the Muslim community, even in providing services to the Muslim minority communities, is of concern. About 20% of the people surveyed by us said that they had no anganwadi centre in their village/ward/locality. It was found that overall 69% of the eligible children did not go to anganwadi centres. The low coverage of the Muslim community in the 'Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) programme continues to remain a concern.

About 39% reported that no woman in the family benefited from nutrition and health education while a significant 25% reported that they did not know anything about any scheme. Only about 19% reported that women in the family had benefited from the scheme. The low rate of benefits from nutrition and health education of the ICDS scheme remains a cause of alarm.

Renewed Political Onslaught

The reproduction of some findings above is to provide a sample of the extent of marginalization of Indian Muslims under the UPA government. The NDA government has stopped short of disowning the Sachar report with the then minister for minorities affairs questioning the minority status of Muslims! They have turned the logic of affirmative action on its head by contending that any special measures for supporting Muslims educationally and economically would amount to religious discrimination of other socio-religious communities such as Hindus! We have seen total inaction on the part of the government in the face of violence and lynching by gau rakshaks and during the Delhi riots. Despite Constitutional definition of equal citizenship for all Indians

irrespective of faith background, the Citizenship Amendment Act has been brought in. Not much action can be expected towards poverty alleviation and inclusion of Muslims despite populist slogans such as sabka saath, sabka vikas, sabka vishwas.

Issues faced during the Pandemic

Our work at the CPS and Bharatiya Muslim Mahila Andolan (BMMA) in ten states suggests that the Muslim community faced major issues during the country-wide lockdown of March-May 2020. Large proportion of the community is employed in the informal sector and very small businesses. Lockdown meant stoppage of income and daily wages leading to the question of ration shortages and hunger. In the middle of this, in some states such as Telangana, the authorities unthinkingly cancelled thousands of ration cards leading to tremendous hardships to those in need. We received complaints about harassment by police during lockdown. A representation on these issues was made by S Q Masood, one of our volunteers in Hyderabad which received a good response from the authorities¹. Lakhs of dry ration kits and food packets were distributed by social organizations and religious groups in different states to support hungry families.

The communalization of the pandemic by mischievous elements including TV channels about Muslims spreading corona jehad went unchecked. FIRs were promptly registered by Delhi police and some 30 individuals were arrested for violating lockdown and social distancing norms. All of them were released almost a year later by the Bombay and Delhi High Courts, which found the allegations unfounded and baseless. But in the meantime, the climate was vitiated resulting in the unacceptable behaviour of police, some hospital personnel and administration personnel in several places. This caused additional harassment for Muslims who tested positive or those who needed health facilities for routine medical problems. There have been reports of Muslim

daily wagers being thrown out of jobs because they “spread virus” under “corona jihad” conspiracy. In cities such as Delhi, Bangalore and Hyderabad civil society activists found Bengali Muslim migrants living in very dismal condition with no food, no water, no sanitation facilities, no attention by authorities throughout the lockdown period.

The volunteers at CPS-BMMA received complaints from women about communal behaviour by hospital personnel in some cities. They talked about mistreatment in civil hospitals, rude behaviour by staff, no attention by doctors in some cases. Some of these complaints may be common across poor communities and may not be confined to Muslims alone. In Jaipur there was been an incident of forced testing of 40 Muslim men based on rumours. All 40 of them turned out to be COVID-19 negative.

We received many complaints from women about domestic violence and increased harassment by husbands and other family members during lockdown. Also, we received complaints from women themselves of at least 6 cases of instant triple talaq during lockdown. We are dealing with increased cases of women in depression with heightened hardships in daily life. The volunteers also find pregnant women facing particular hardships in the absence of special care in hospitals and at home owing to inability to afford necessities. There is a big need for hygiene related measures in Muslim ghettos in cities. Women suffer because of lack of menstrual hygiene measures owing to expenses involved apart from lack of access to soaps and sanitizers during pandemic. With closure of schools, there are no avenues for children to keep busy. They have neither computers nor smart phones to participate in online classes or other educational activities. This is leading to further complications for children and women within families. Most Muslim women are engaged in low paying home-based economic activity. They depend on middle-men to provide job work to them. This meagre

economic support is affected as the supply chain linkages are broken down during the pandemic.

Community awareness and education about the pandemic is still lacking completely. In 2020, many people in Muslim neighbourhoods were confused owing to contradictory messages from different quarters. There is no secular democratic leadership within the community and the barely literate maulvis are in no position to guide them. In fact, most maulvis and religious figures preach fatalism by asking worshippers to leave everything to Allah! Of course, there is no need for masks or sanitizers or physical distancing as Allah will protect every Muslim from the virus! This led to confusion and conflicting messages for ordinary persons. Many were not sure and were asking questions such as whether the pandemic is real or is it some rumour? Is it a conspiracy by some elements? Years of negligence and apathy from authorities has led to a trust deficit between the community and governmental agencies. Most families live in small 1-2 room homes in ghettos in urban places making physical distancing next to impossible. There are no sources of credible scientific information within the community.

Poverty, low education, lack of healthcare are not the only factors that have come in the way of the Muslim community fighting the pandemic. The general lack of awareness about the pandemic led to continuation of mass namaz gatherings in Muslim-dominated localities in most cities. Ramzan Eid was celebrated with untampered gaiety in most cities in 2020 and again in May 2021. Men and children could be seen going around without masks in most places as reported by several volunteers within the community apart from I seeing it myself. The need for masks may not be felt by burqa-clad women but the same does not hold for others in the family. The second wave in April-May 2021 brought out the intense shortage of vaccines nationally on the one hand and on the other, there has been a huge vaccine hesitancy amongst people living in the Muslim ghettos. It is observed that

the vaccine hesitancy still continues and must be addressed urgently. There are a number of media reports highlighting this.

Way Forward

There is a need for a systematic community education campaign about the effects of the pandemic and the inevitability of the change towards appropriate behaviour such as masks and physical distancing. There should be a comprehensive community outreach program in Muslim neighbourhoods as most persons there have low formal education and lack access to scientific information. Local government agencies and civil society must come together to educate the community about the pandemic and to ensure that every adult is vaccinated. The local agencies must take special measures to make announcements in mosques through microphones, posters in different languages and pictorials for need to vaccinate.

Conclusions

Needless to say, the government must take urgent steps to rein in those attempting to communalize the fight against COVID-19 without which the virus cannot be defeated. Punitive action must be taken against those spreading fake news in the media branding Muslim ghettos as COVID-19 hubs. Steps must be taken to sensitize health workers about Muslims being equal Indian citizens and penalize those who discriminate with them. Hospitals and police should show empathy rather than hatred based on prejudices.

I am not in the least suggesting that these special measures should be taken for Muslims on account of their religion. I am advocating these measures to include them as just as we take special measures to include poor and marginalized sections in every governmental program or scheme. Ordinary Muslims are

the most excluded and often misunderstood sections of our democratic society. Besides, this needs to be done by all socially conscious agencies as there is no secular democratic leadership in the community, which can take up the challenge to fight the pandemic. The fight against the pandemic cannot be successful without inclusion of the largest minority.

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ⁱ Annexure 1 – Response to S Q Masood's representation by
Telangana High Court

Annex 1: Response to S Q Masood's representation by Telangana High Court

[3164]

(SHOW CAUSE NOTICE BEFORE ADMISSION)
IN THE HIGH COURT FOR THE STATE OF TELANGANA
AT HYDERABAD
MONDAY, THE TWENTY SEVENTH DAY OF APRIL
TWO THOUSAND AND TWENTY
: PRESENT:
THE HON'BLE THE CHIEF JUSTICE SRI RAGHVENDRA SINGH CHAUHAN
AND
THE HON'BLE SRI JUSTICE A.ABHISHEK REDDY
WP(PIL) NO: 72 OF 2020

Between:
Mr. S.Q.Masood, Social Activist, H.No.19-2-21/23/39, Basharith Nagar, Macca Colony,
Hyderabad 500 053. M.9030557002 sqmasood@gmail.com

Petitioner

AND

1. State of Telangana, Rep. by its Chief Secretary, Secretariat, Hyderabad.
2. State of Telangana, Represented by its Principal Secretary, Home Department, Secretariat, Hyderabad.
3. The Director General of Police, State of Telangana, Lakdikapool, Hyderabad.
4. State of Telangana, Represented by its Principal Secretary, Medical and Health Department, Secretariat, Hyderabad.
5. The Director of Medical and Health, Government of Telangana, Koti, Hyderabad.

Respondents

WHEREAS the Petitioner above named through Letter dated 16.04.2020 sent by him through email, under Constitution of India, praying that in the circumstances stated in the letter dated 16.04.2020, the Hon'ble Court may be pleased to issue an appropriate Writ, Order or Orders more particularly, one in the nature of a Writ of Mandamus to call for remarks and records from the Respondents herein relating to and in connection with police brutality on general public, journalists, social workers during COVID-19 lockdown in Hyderabad though State Government has allowed to operate essential goods and services, Banks/ATMs and related activities, Print and electronic media, IT and ITes, including telecom, postal and internet Services, Supply chain and transport of essential commodities, E-Commerce (delivery) of essential goods including food, pharmaceutical and medical equipment, sale of food items, groceries, milk, bread, fruits, vegetables, eggs, meat, fish and their transportation and warehousing activities, Take-away home delivery at restaurants, Hospitals, optical stores, diagnostic centres, pharmaceuticals manufacturing and their transportation, Petrol pumps, LPG gas, oil agencies, their godowns and their related transport operations, all security services including those provided by private agencies, Private establishments that support the provisioning of essential services or the efforts for containment of COVID-19 and as per the government order, essential services were allowed from 6am to 7pm after which movement of the individuals are completely restricted, but a number of videos circulating on social media showed police men thrashing passers by and motorists in various parts of the city, and were manhandled being beaten with lathis and incidents of such misbehaviour have been reported from across the State, indicating that they reflect a problem with the fundamental character of the police, treating this situation as law and order issues and there is a high need to sensitise police personnel to deal with the situation. Consequently, to constitute a High Level Committee under the Chairmanship of Chairman/Member Secretary, State Legal Services Authority at State level and at District Legal Services Authority at District level to look into these incidents of police brutality and other issues as per legal services authority Scheme for legal services to Disaster Victims through legal services authorities under Sub clause (e) of Section 12 of Legal Services Authorities Act 1987 immediately, and to direct the respondents herein to b) Ensure that all police personnel are made aware of the limits of the statutory provisions as well as the conditions set under the MHA Guidelines, c) To pass appropriate orders to quash cases booked and release all vehicles seized during the lockdown, d) The government to give wider publicity about consequences if people violate government orders through news papers and public address system e) The government for strict enforcement of the lockdown by calling and deputing additional police forces and barricading the areas, f) Police Department and GHMC to develop a process to issue passes in fair and easy manner at PS and ward level, g) Government to open local clinics, hospitals and out patient operations in every hospitals with strict conditions to maintain social distancing and other important measures to control spreading of Covid-19 h) Police department to conduct sensitisation programmes for police personnel on how to deal with general public at this tough time of lockdown in view of Covid-19;

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doi:

AND WHEREAS the High Court upon perusing the letter dated 16.04.2020 filed herein and upon hearing the arguments Sri B.S. Prasad, Advocate General for the respondent No. 1 to 4, directed issue of notice to the Respondent No. 5 returnable in two weeks, herein to show cause as to why this PUBLIC INTEREST LITIGATION should not be admitted.

You viz:

The Director of Medical and Health, Government of Telangana, Koti, Hyderabad.

are directed to show cause as to why in the circumstances set out in the petition filed therewith (copy enclosed) this PUBLIC INTEREST LITIGATION should not be admitted.
The Court made the following

ORDER:

Mr. B.S. Prasad, the learned Advocate General, takes notice on behalf of respondent Nos. 1 to 4.

Issue notice to respondent No. 5 returnable in two weeks.

List this case after two weeks.

Sd/- LNAGA LAKSHMI
ASSISTANT REGISTRAR

//TRUE COPY//

SECTION OFFICER

To,

1. The Director of Medical and Health, Government of Telangana, Koti, Hyderabad. (by RPAD- along with a copy of petition and Affidavit)
 2. Two CC to Advocate General, High Court, Hyderabad (OUT)
 3. Two spare copies
- Csk

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HIGH COURT

HCJ
&
AARJ

DATED:27/04/2020

NOTE: POST AFTER TWO WEEKS

NOTICE BEFORE ADMISSION

WP(PIL).No.72 of 2020

